

Path-based origin-destination matrix estimation utilising macroscopic traffic dynamics

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Supplementary material

1 The signalised path-based CTM

Upstream boundary connection.

- An *entering* connection ($i^- \in \mathcal{E}$), shown in Figure 1 (a), is at the endpoint of the network where traffic enters the upstream of cell $i \in \mathcal{L}$ directly from the outside. We denote as $\tilde{u}_p(k)$ the flow of vehicles entering the network through path $p \in \mathcal{P}_i$ at time $k \in \mathcal{T}^+$. Summing over all paths passing through cell i , where $i^- \in \mathcal{E}$, results in the total demand that requests to enter the network from the outside, $D_i^{in}(k) = \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}_i} \tilde{u}_p(k)$. The inflow and the per path inflow of cell i and path $p \in \mathcal{P}_i$ at time-step k are given respectively by

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\varphi}_i^{in}(k) &= \min \left\{ \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}_i} \tilde{u}_p(k), S_i(k) \right\}, \\ \varphi_{i,p}^{in}(k) &= \frac{\tilde{u}_p(k)}{\sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}_i} \tilde{u}_p(k)} \min \left\{ \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}_i} \tilde{u}_p(k), S_i(k) \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

- An *ordinary* upstream boundary connection ($i^- \in \mathcal{O}$), shown in Figure 1 (b), has one upstream cell j and traffic enters the upstream of cell $i \in \mathcal{L}$ from cell $j \in \mathcal{L}$. The inflow of cell i is

$$\bar{\varphi}_i^{in}(k) = h_j(k) \min \{D_j(k), S_i(k)\}, \quad j \in \mathcal{N}_i^-, \quad (2)$$

and the per path inflow of i at time-step k is

$$\varphi_{i,p}^{in}(k) = h_j(k) \frac{\rho_{j,p}(k)}{\sum_{b \in \mathcal{P}_j} \rho_{j,b}(k)} \min \{D_j(k), S_i(k)\}, \quad (3)$$

$j \in \mathcal{N}_i^-$, $p \in \mathcal{P}_i \cap \mathcal{P}_j$, where $h_j(k)$ is the traffic light that regulates traffic proceeding

from cell $j \in \mathcal{N}_i^-$ to cell i . Equation (3) suggests that if the flow from link j is restricted by the supply of cell i then cell i enters the congested regime and its demand takes the maximum flow, φ_i^{max} , and all paths passing through cell i are constrained proportionally to their density by $\rho_{j,p}(k)/[\sum_{b \in \mathcal{P}_j} \rho_{j,b}(k)]$.

- In a *merging* upstream connection ($i^- \in \mathcal{M}$) two or more cells merge in the upstream connection of cell i as shown in Figure 1 (d). The inflow of cell i is expressed as the sum of outflows of all upstream cells $j \in \mathcal{N}_i^-$, $\bar{\varphi}_i^{in}(k) = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^-} h_j(k) \bar{\varphi}_j^{out}(k)$. The outflow of cell $j \in \mathcal{N}_i^-$ at time-step k is $\bar{\varphi}_j^{out}(k) = D_{ji}(k) \min \left\{ 1, S_i(k) / \sum_{j' \in \mathcal{N}_i^-} h_{j'}(k) D_{ji'}(k) \right\}$, where $D_{ji}(k)$ is the demand of cell j that requests to enter cell i at time-step k given as

$$D_{ji}(k) = \frac{\sum_{b \in \mathcal{P}_i \cap \mathcal{P}_j} \rho_{j,b}(k)}{\bar{\rho}_j(k)} D_j(k), \quad (4)$$

which basically ensures that outflows are allocated proportionally to their per path densities. If the total demand of cells $j \in \mathcal{N}_i^-$, is restricted by the supply of cell i , $S_i(k) < \sum_{j' \in \mathcal{N}_i^-} h_{j'}(k) D_{ji'}(k)$, then the outflow of each cell j is given proportionally to its demand $D_{ji}(k)$. Hence the inflow of cell i is

$$\bar{\varphi}_i^{in}(k) = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^-} h_j(k) D_{ji}(k) \min \left\{ 1, \frac{S_i(k)}{\sum_{j' \in \mathcal{N}_i^-} h_{j'}(k) D_{ji'}(k)} \right\}. \quad (5)$$

The per path inflow of cell i is equal to the per path outflow of cell $j \in \mathcal{N}_i^-$ for which $p \in \mathcal{P}_i \cap \mathcal{P}_j$ and is given by

$$\varphi_{i,p}^{in}(k) = h_j(k) \frac{\rho_{j,p}(k)}{\bar{\rho}_j(k)} D_j(k) \min \left\{ 1, \frac{S_i(k)}{\sum_{j' \in \mathcal{N}_i^-} h_{j'}(k) D_{ji'}(k)} \right\}, \quad (6)$$

$p \in \mathcal{P}_i \cap \mathcal{P}_j$. Equation (6) ensures that inflows get the portion of supply allocated to them based on their per path densities.

Downstream boundary connection.

- An *exiting* connection ($i^+ \in \mathcal{G}$) is at the endpoint of the network where traffic exits the downstream boundary of cell i to the outside of the network with free-flow speed v_i^f , as shown in Figure 1 (e). The outflow and the per path outflow of cell i are

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\varphi}_i^{out}(k) &= v_i^f \bar{\rho}_i(k), \\ \varphi_{i,p}^{out}(k) &= v_i^f \rho_{i,p}(k), \quad p \in \mathcal{P}_i. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Note that for the exiting boundary connection we assume that $h_i(k) = 1, \forall k \in \mathcal{T}^+$.

- An *ordinary* downstream boundary connection ($i^+ \in \mathcal{O}$), shown in Figure 1 (f), has one downstream cell and traffic proceeds from cell i directly to cell j . The outflow and the per

path outflow of i at k is

$$\begin{aligned}\bar{\varphi}_i^{out}(k) &= \min \{D_i(k), S_j(k)\}, j \in \mathcal{N}_i^+, \\ \varphi_{i,p}^{out}(k) &= \frac{\rho_{i,p}(k)}{\bar{\rho}_i(k)} \min \{D_i(k), S_j(k)\},\end{aligned}\quad (8)$$

$p \in \mathcal{P}_i \cap \mathcal{P}_j, j \in \mathcal{N}_i^+$, which as before is obtained proportionally to its path density $\rho_{i,p}(k)$.

- In a *diverging* downstream connection ($i^+ \in \mathcal{D}$), cell i diverges into two or more cells ($j \in \mathcal{N}_i^+$) as shown in Figure 1 (g). We denote as $D_{ij}(k)$ the demand of cell i that requests to enter cell j at time k given as $D_{ij}(k) = \{[\sum_{b \in \mathcal{P}_i \cap \mathcal{P}_j} \rho_{i,b}(k)]/\bar{\rho}_i(k)\}D_i(k)$, $j \in \mathcal{N}_i^+$, meaning that the demand for each cell j is given proportionally to path densities with $p \in \mathcal{P}_i \cap \mathcal{P}_j$ and $j \in \mathcal{N}_i^+$. The sum of all demands $D_{ij}(k)$, $j \in \mathcal{N}_i^+$, results in the total demand of cell i : $D_i(k) = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^+} D_{ij}(k)$. The outflow of cell i can be expressed as the sum of inflow of all cells $j \in \mathcal{N}_i^+$, $\bar{\varphi}_i^{out}(k) = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^+} \bar{\varphi}_j^{in}(k)$, while the inflow of its downstream cells $j \in \mathcal{N}_i^+$ is given by

$$\bar{\varphi}_j^{in}(k) = D_{ij}(k) \min \left\{ 1, \left\{ \frac{S_{\hat{j}}(k)}{D_{i\hat{j}}(k)} \right\}_{\hat{j} \in \mathcal{N}_i^+} \right\}.$$

The above expression implies that if there exists a downstream neighbour $\hat{j} \in \mathcal{N}_i^+$ for which the demand $D_{i\hat{j}}(k)$ is restricted by the supply of cell \hat{j} , $S_{\hat{j}}(k) < D_{i\hat{j}}(k)$ then the inflow of all cells $j \in \mathcal{N}_i^+$ is equally restricted by the ratio $S_{\hat{j}}(k)/D_{i\hat{j}}(k)$ as shown in the above equation. Hence the outflow of cell i is

$$\bar{\varphi}_i^{out}(k) = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^+} D_{ij}(k) \min \left\{ 1, \left\{ \frac{S_{\hat{j}}(k)}{D_{i\hat{j}}(k)} \right\}_{\hat{j} \in \mathcal{N}_i^+} \right\}. \quad (9)$$

Similarly, the outflow of cell i per path $p \in \mathcal{P}_i$ is

$$\varphi_{i,p}^{out}(k) = \frac{\rho_{i,p}(k)}{\bar{\rho}_i(k)} D_i(k) \min \left\{ 1, \left\{ \frac{S_{\hat{j}}(k)}{D_{i\hat{j}}(k)} \right\}_{\hat{j} \in \mathcal{N}_i^+} \right\}, \quad (10)$$

$p \in \mathcal{P}_i \cap \mathcal{P}_j, j \in \mathcal{N}_i^+$ and is proportional to $\rho_{i,p}(k)$.

2 Partial Derivatives for calculating the Jacobian matrix $\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{z})$

The analytical derivatives presented in Section V depend on the partial derivatives of cell and per path inflows and outflows with respect to cell and per path densities, which differ for the different boundary connections. As shown in Equations (31)-(32) for each set of summations in the equation, the first term (e.g. $\partial \varphi_j^{in}(k)/\partial \bar{\rho}_j(k)$) is known and given at the specific location of the Jacobian at time-step k , $\mathbf{J}^{(k)}(\mathbf{z})$. The partial derivative of the second term depends on the boundary characterisation of each cell as follows.

Upstream boundary connections

- Entering connection: When the upstream of cell $i \in \mathcal{L}$ is characterised by an entering connection, see Equations (13), the partial derivatives of the inflow of the cell are given by

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial \bar{\varphi}_i^{in}(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)} &= \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}_i} u_p(k) < S_i(k) \\ \frac{\partial S_i(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ \frac{\partial \bar{\varphi}_i^{in}(k)}{\partial \rho_m(k)} &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial \bar{\varphi}_i^{in}(k)}{\partial u_q} &= \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } q \in \mathcal{P}_i \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}\end{aligned}$$

where $h = 1, \dots, L$, $m = 1, \dots, M$ and $q = 1, \dots, Q$. Subscript m maps the 2-D index $\{j, p\}$, $p \in \mathcal{P}_j$, $j \in \mathcal{N}_i^-$ and $j = 1, \dots, L$ as described in Section V. The partial derivatives of the per path inflow are

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial \varphi_i^{in}(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)} &= \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}_i} u_p(k) < S_i(k) \\ \frac{u_p(k)}{\sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}_i} u_p(k)} \frac{\partial S_i(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ \frac{\partial \varphi_i^{in}(k)}{\partial \rho_m(k)} &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial \varphi_i^{in}(k)}{\partial u_q} &= \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } q \in \mathcal{P}_i \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}\end{aligned}$$

To obtain the above, the partial derivative of the supply of cell i with respect to the cell density $\bar{\rho}_h(k)$ may be needed which is given by

$$\frac{\partial S_i(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)} = \begin{cases} -u_i^b, & \text{if } u_i^b \bar{\rho}_i(k) \geq u_i^b \rho_i^{max} - \varphi_i^{max} \text{ and } i = h \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

The inflow does not directly depend on $\bar{\rho}_h(k)$ and $\rho_m(k)$ as presented in Equation (13), hence these derivatives will be equal to zero, except the special case that the sum of all flows entering cell i for paths $p \in \mathcal{P}_i$ is larger than the supply of the specific cell.

- Ordinary connection: An ordinary upstream boundary connection, as shown in Equations (14) - (15), does not depend on u_p and hence the partial derivatives with respect to u_p are zero. The partial derivatives with respect to $\bar{\rho}_h(k)$, $h = 1, \dots, L$, and $\rho_m(k)$, $m = 1, \dots, M$, for the cell inflow are given as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial \bar{\varphi}_i^{in}(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)} &= h_j(k) \begin{cases} \frac{\partial D_j(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)}, & \text{if } D_j(k) \leq S_i(k), j \in \mathcal{N}_i^- \\ \frac{\partial S_i(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ \frac{\partial \bar{\varphi}_i^{in}(k)}{\partial \rho_m(k)} &= 0\end{aligned}$$

The partial derivatives with respect to $\bar{\rho}_h(k)$ and $\rho_m(k)$, for the per path inflow are

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial \varphi_l^{in}(k)}{\partial \rho_m(k)} &= \frac{1}{\bar{\rho}_j(k)} \min\{D_j(k), S_i(k)\} \mathbb{1}_{w=m} \\ \frac{\partial \varphi_l^{in}(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)} &= -\frac{\rho_w(k)}{\bar{\rho}_j(k)} \min\{D_j(k), S_i(k)\} \mathbb{1}_{j=h} + \frac{\rho_w(k)}{\bar{\rho}_j(k)} \begin{cases} \frac{\partial D_j(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)}, & \text{if } D_j(k) \leq S_i(k) \\ \frac{\partial S_i(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)}, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}\end{aligned}$$

where, similar to m , w maps the 2-D index $\{j, p\}$, $p \in \mathcal{P}_j$, $j \in \mathcal{N}_i^-$ and $j = 1, \dots, L$, $w = 1, \dots, M$. To obtain the above expressions, the partial derivative of the demand and the supply of cell i with respect to the cell density $\bar{\rho}_h(k)$ are needed, with $\partial S_i(k)/\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)$ given in Equation (11) and the partial derivative for the demand given by

$$\frac{\partial D_j(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)} = \begin{cases} v_j^f, & \text{if } v_j^f \bar{\rho}_j(k) \leq \varphi_j^{max} \text{ and } j = h \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

In addition the partial derivatives of the demand and supply with respect to the per path densities are equal to zero as they do not depend directly on these:

$$\frac{\partial D_j(k)}{\partial \rho_m(k)} = \frac{\partial S_i(k)}{\partial \rho_m(k)} = 0 \quad (13)$$

- Merging connection: The cell and per path inflow are given by Equations (17) - (18) as described in Section III-B. The partial derivatives of the cell inflow with respect to the cell density $\bar{\rho}_h(k)$, $h = 1, \dots, L$, and the per path densities $\rho_m(k)$, $m = 1, \dots, M$, are given by

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial \bar{\varphi}_i^{in}(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)} &= \begin{cases} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^-} h_j(k) \frac{\partial D_{ji}(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)}, & \text{if } S_i(k) \geq \sum_{j' \in \mathcal{N}_i^-} D_{j'i}(k) \\ \frac{\partial S_i(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ \frac{\partial \bar{\varphi}_i^{in}(k)}{\partial \rho_m(k)} &= \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^-} h_j(k) \frac{\partial D_{ji}(k)}{\partial \rho_m(k)} \mathbb{1}_{[S_i(k) \geq \sum_{j' \in \mathcal{N}_i^-} D_{j'i}(k)]}\end{aligned}$$

and the partial derivative of the per path inflow with respect to $\rho_m(k)$ is

$$\frac{\partial \varphi_l^{in}(k)}{\partial \rho_m(k)} = \begin{cases} h_j(k) \frac{1}{\bar{\rho}_j(k)} D_j(k) \mathbb{1}_{w=m}, & \text{if } S_i(k) \geq \sum_{j' \in \mathcal{N}_i^-} h_{j'}(k) D_{j'i}(k) \\ -h_j(k) \frac{\rho_w(k)}{\bar{\rho}_j(k)} D_j(k) S_i(k) \frac{\sum_{j' \in \mathcal{N}_i^-} h_{j'}(k) \frac{\partial D_{j'i}(k)}{\partial \rho_m(k)}}{\left[\sum_{j' \in \mathcal{N}_i^-} h_{j'} D_{j'i}(k)\right]^2} + \frac{h_j(k) D_j(k) S_i(k)}{\bar{\rho}_j(k) \sum_{j' \in \mathcal{N}_i^-} h_{j'}(k) D_{j'i}(k)} \mathbb{1}_{w=m}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

For the partial derivative of the per path inflow with respect to $\bar{\rho}_h(k)$, if $S_i(k) \geq \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^-} h_j(k) D_{ji}(k)$ then the derivative is given by

$$\frac{\partial \varphi_l^{in}(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)} = -h_j(k) \frac{\rho_w(k)}{\bar{\rho}_j(k)} D_j(k) \frac{S_i(k)}{\sum_{j' \in \mathcal{N}_i^-} h_{j'}(k) D_{j'i}(k)} \mathbb{1}_{j=h} + h_j(k) \frac{\rho_w(k)}{\bar{\rho}_j(k)} \frac{\partial D_j(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)}$$

otherwise, i.e. if $S_i(k) < \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^-} h_j(k) D_{ji}(k)$, the partial derivative is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \varphi_i^{in}(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)} = h_j(k) & \left[\frac{\rho_w(k)}{\bar{\rho}_j(k)} \frac{\partial D_j(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)} \frac{S_i(k)}{\sum_{j' \in \mathcal{N}_i^-} h_{j'}(k) D_{j'i}(k)} - \frac{\rho_w(k)}{[\bar{\rho}_j(k)]^2} \frac{D_j(k) S_i(k)}{\sum_{j' \in \mathcal{N}_i^-} h_{j'}(k) D_{j'i}(k)} \right] \mathbb{1}_{j=h} \\ & + \frac{\frac{\rho_w(k)}{\bar{\rho}_j(k)} D_j(k) \frac{\partial S_i(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)}}{\sum_{j' \in \mathcal{N}_i^-} h_{j'}(k) D_{j'i}(k)} - \frac{\frac{\rho_w(k)}{\bar{\rho}_j(k)} D_j(k) S_i(k) \sum_{j' \in \mathcal{N}_i^-} \frac{\partial D_{j'i}(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)}}{\left[\sum_{j' \in \mathcal{N}_i^-} h_{j'}(k) D_{j'i}(k) \right]^2} \end{aligned}$$

The partial derivatives of the demand and supply with respect to a cell densities are given by (12) and (11), respectively. In addition, the partial derivatives of $D_{ji}(k)$, $j \in \mathcal{N}_i^-$, with respect to the cell and per path densities are required and given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial D_{ji}(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)} &= \left[-\frac{\sum_{w \in \mathcal{L}_i^{in} \cap \mathcal{L}_j^{in}} \rho_w(k)}{[\bar{\rho}_j(k)]^2} D_j(k) + \frac{\sum_{w \in \mathcal{L}_i^{in} \cap \mathcal{L}_j^{in}} \rho_w(k)}{\bar{\rho}_j(k)} \frac{\partial D_j(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)} \right] \mathbb{1}_{j=h} \\ \frac{\partial D_{ji}(k)}{\partial \rho_m(k)} &= \frac{1}{\bar{\rho}_j(k)} D_j(k) \mathbb{1}_{w=m} \end{aligned}$$

Downstream boundary connections

- **Exiting connection:** The cell and per path outflow of an exiting downstream connection are given in Equations (19). The partial derivatives of cell outflow with respect to the cell and per path densities, $\bar{\rho}_h(k)$, $h = 1 \dots, L$ and $\rho_m(k)$, $m = 1, \dots, M$, respectively, are given as

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\varphi}_i^{out}(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)} = v_i^f \mathbb{1}_{i=h} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial \bar{\varphi}_i^{out}(k)}{\partial \rho_m(k)} = 0$$

and the partial derivatives of per path outflow with respect to the cell and per path densities are

$$\frac{\partial \varphi_l^{out}(k)}{\partial \rho_m(k)} = v_i^f \mathbb{1}_{l=m} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial \varphi_l^{out}(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)} = 0.$$

- **Ordinary Connection:** The cell and per path outflow of an ordinary downstream boundary connection are given by Equations (20). The partial derivatives of the cell outflow with respect to the cell and per path densities, $\bar{\rho}_h(k)$, $h = 1 \dots, L$ and $\rho_m(k)$, $m = 1, \dots, M$, respectively, are given as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \bar{\varphi}_i^{out}(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)} &= \begin{cases} \frac{\partial D_i(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)}, & \text{if } D_i(k) \leq S_j(k) \\ \frac{\partial S_j(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ \frac{\partial \bar{\varphi}_i^{out}(k)}{\partial \rho_m(k)} &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

The partial derivatives of the per path outflow with respect to $\bar{\rho}_h(k)$, and $\rho_m(k)$ are

$$\frac{\partial \varphi_l^{out}(k)}{\partial \rho_m(k)} = \frac{1}{\bar{\rho}_i(k)} \min\{D_i(k), S_j(k)\} \mathbb{1}_{l=m}$$

$$\frac{\partial \varphi_l^{out}(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)} = -\frac{\rho_l(k)}{\bar{\rho}_i(k)} \min\{D_i(k), S_j(k)\} \mathbb{1}_{i=h} + \frac{\rho_l(k)}{\bar{\rho}_i(k)} \begin{cases} \frac{\partial D_i(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)}, & \text{if } D_i(k) \leq S_j(k) \\ \frac{\partial S_j(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

To obtain the above the partial derivatives of the demand and supply with respect to cell densities $\bar{\rho}_h(k)$ are needed and these are given by Equations (12) and (11), respectively.

- **Diverging Connection:** The cell and per path outflows are given by Equations (21) and (22), respectively. To obtain the partial derivatives of cell outflow with respect to cell and per path densities, $\bar{\rho}_h(k)$, $h = 1, \dots, L$, and $\rho_m(k)$, $m = 1, \dots, M$, we first set

$$\frac{A(k)}{B(k)} = \min \left\{ \frac{S_{j'}(k)}{D_{ij'}(k)} \right\}_{j' \in \mathcal{N}_i^+},$$

such that $A(k)$ corresponds to the supply of the specific downstream cell $\tilde{j} \in \mathcal{N}_i^+$, $S_{\tilde{j}}(k)$ and $B(k)$ to $D_{i\tilde{j}}(k)$ that results in the lowest ratio $A(k)/B(k)$ at time-step k . Then the cell outflow partial derivatives are given as follows.

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\varphi}_i^{out}(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)} = \begin{cases} \frac{\partial D_i(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)} \mathbb{1}_{S_j(k) \geq D_{ij}(k), \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_i^+} \\ \left[\frac{\partial D_i(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)} \frac{A(k)}{B(k)} + D_i(k) \frac{\frac{\partial A(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)} B(k) - A(k) \frac{\partial B(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)}}{B(k)^2} \right] \mathbb{1}_{S_j(k) > D_{ij}(k), \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_i^+} \end{cases}$$

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\varphi}_i^{out}(k)}{\partial \rho_m(k)} = \begin{cases} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^+} \frac{\partial D_{ij}(k)}{\partial \rho_m(k)} \mathbb{1}_{S_j(k) \geq D_{ij}(k), \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_i^+} \\ \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^+} \frac{\partial D_{ij}(k)}{\partial \rho_m(k)} \frac{A(k)}{B(k)} - \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^+} D_{ij}(k) \frac{A(k) \frac{\partial B(k)}{\partial \rho_m(k)}}{B(k)^2} \end{cases}$$

The partial derivative of the per path outflow with respect to $\rho_m(k)$ is given by:

$$\frac{\partial \varphi_l^{out}(k)}{\partial \rho_m(k)} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\bar{\rho}_i(k)} D_i(k) \mathbb{1}_{l=m}, & \text{if } S_j(k) \geq D_{ij}(k), \forall j \in \mathcal{N}_i^+ \\ -\frac{\rho_l(k)}{\bar{\rho}_i(k)} D_i(k) \frac{A(k) \frac{\partial B(k)}{\partial \rho_m(k)}}{B(k)^2} + \frac{1}{\bar{\rho}_i(k)} D_i(k) \frac{A(k)}{B(k)} \mathbb{1}_{l=m}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

For the partial derivative of the per path outflow with respect to $\bar{\rho}_h(k)$, if $S_j(k) \geq D_{ij}(k)$, $\forall j \in \mathcal{N}_i^+$ we have that

$$\frac{\partial \varphi_l^{out}(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)} = \left[-\frac{\rho_l(k)}{\bar{\rho}_i(k)} D_i(k) + \frac{\rho_l(k)}{\bar{\rho}_i(k)} \frac{\partial D_i(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)} \right] \mathbb{1}_{i=h}$$

otherwise, i.e. if $S_{\tilde{j}}(k) < D_{i\tilde{j}}(k)$, $\tilde{j} \in \mathcal{N}_i^+$, the partial derivative is given by

$$\frac{\partial \varphi_l^{out}(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)} = \frac{\rho_l(k)}{\bar{\rho}_i(k)} D_i(k) \frac{\frac{\partial A(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)} B(k) - A(k) \frac{\partial B(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)}}{B(k)^2} - \left[\frac{\rho_l(k)}{\bar{\rho}_i(k)} D_i(k) \frac{A(k)}{B(k)} - \frac{\rho_l(k)}{\bar{\rho}_i(k)} \frac{\partial D_i(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)} \frac{A(k)}{B(k)} \right] \mathbb{1}_{i=h}.$$

To obtain the above the partial derivatives of the demand and supply with respect to cell densities $\bar{\rho}_i(k)$ are needed and these are given by Equations (12) and (11), respectively. In addition the partial derivatives of $D_{ij}(k)$, $j \in \mathcal{N}_i^+$, with respect to the cell and per path densities are required and given by:

$$\frac{\partial D_{ij}(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)} = \left[\frac{-\sum_{w \in \mathcal{L}_i^{out} \cap \mathcal{L}_j^{out}} \rho_w(k)}{[\bar{\rho}_i(k)]^2} D_i(k) + \frac{\sum_{w \in \mathcal{L}_i^{out} \cap \mathcal{L}_j^{out}} \rho_w(k)}{\bar{\rho}_i(k)} \frac{\partial D_i(k)}{\partial \bar{\rho}_h(k)} \right] \mathbb{1}_{i=h}$$

$$\frac{\partial D_{ij}(k)}{\partial \rho_m(k)} = \frac{1}{\bar{\rho}_i(k)} D_i(k) \mathbb{1}_{w=m}$$

The above derivatives combined with Equations (32) - (33) are sufficient to provide the Jacobian matrix, $\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{z})$ needed to assist the optimisation procedure in the general solution approach that is detailed described in Section V.

3 Network-specific parameters

3.1 Leicester network

We assume that the network consists of 9 OD pairs and each OD pair has 1-5 paths over which the OD flows are distributed, as shown in Table 1. More specifically, we consider the following OD pairs:

$$\{W_1W_{11}, W_1W_{20}, W_1W_{21}, W_{17}W_{20}, W_{17}W_{21}, W_3W_{20}, W_9W_{10}, W_{15}W_{11}, W_3W_{11}\}.$$

Note that OD pairs are presented as a combination of nodes, with the first node denoting the origin and the second node the destination node. We assume 25 candidate paths while only 15 paths are carrying demand as indicated in Table 1. Paths are given as an ordered set of cells from which each path is passing. As mentioned in the paper, we run the optimisation method $\tilde{B} = 50$ times and at each run of the optimisation procedure we assume that different values of the input vector are considered and different cells are measured in order to minimise biases that might occur from removing sensors associated with a particular OD pair. The path demand, i.e. the input vector, for each scenario, free-flow and congested, for each run of the optimisation procedure is obtained through a normal distribution with mean the values given in Table 1 and variance equal to 10% of the mean value for the free-flow scenario and 20% for the congested scenario.

	OD pair	Candidate paths	Paths carrying demand	Path demand, \mathbf{u} (veh/h) (free-flow)	Path demand, \mathbf{u} (veh/h) (congestion)
1	W_1W_{11}	1→7 → 11→15→22	No	-	-
2	W_1W_{11}	1→7 → 13→14→19→20→21→25	Yes	60	120
3	W_1W_{11}	1→7 → 13→14→17→ 22	No	-	-
4	W_1W_{11}	2→4 → 8→9→15 → 22	Yes	80	

5	W_1W_{20}	1→7 → 13→14→17→18	Yes	50	160
6	W_1W_{20}	1→7 → 11→12→16	Yes	70	100
7	W_1W_{20}	1→7 → 11→15→18	No	-	-
8	W_1W_{20}	2→4 → 8→9→15 → 18	No	-	-
9	W_1W_{20}	2→4 → 5→10→16	No	-	-
10	W_1W_{20}	2→4 → 8→9→12 →16	Yes	75	75
11	W_1W_{21}	2→4 → 5→6	Yes	30	60
12	$W_{17}W_{20}$	3→8 → 9→12→16	Yes	35	80
13	$W_{17}W_{20}$	3→8 → 9→15→18	No	-	-
14	$W_{17}W_{20}$	3→5 → 10→16	Yes	30	45
15	$W_{17}W_{21}$	3→5 → 6	Yes	90	150
16	W_9W_{10}	23 → 24	Yes	50	90
18	$W_{15}W_{11}$	4 → 8→9→15 → 22	Yes	70	70
19	W_3W_{11}	13 → 14→19→20 → 21→ 25	No	-	-
20	W_3W_{11}	13 → 14→17→22	Yes	80	80
21	W_3W_{11}	11 → 15→22	Yes	100	130
22	W_3W_{20}	13 → 14→17→ 18 → 16	No	-	-
23	W_3W_{20}	11 → 15→18	Yes	55	110
24	W_3W_{20}	13 → 14→17→ 18	No	-	-
25	W_3W_{20}	11 → 12→16	No	-	-

Table 1: Paths and path demand considered for the Leicester network.

3.2 Nguyen-Dupuis network

Similarly, for Nguyen-Dupuis network we assume that the network consists of 20 OD pairs and each OD pair has 1-6 paths over which the OD flows are distributed, as shown in Table 2. More specifically, we consider the following OD pairs:

$$\{W_{10}W_{34}, W_{10}W_{56}, W_{10}W_{48}, W_7W_{48}, W_7W_{56}, W_7W_{34}, W_7W_{35}, W_7W_{22}, W_1W_{48}, W_1W_{56}, \\ W_1W_{34}, W_1W_{35}, W_1W_{22}, W_4W_{48}, W_4W_{56}, W_4W_{34}, W_1W_{51}, W_7W_{33}, W_7W_{51}, W_1W_{33}\}.$$

As before, OD pairs are presented as a combination of nodes, with the first node denoting the origin and the second node the destination node, while paths are given as an ordered set of cells from which each path is passing. We assume 70 candidate paths while only 45 paths are carrying demand as indicated in Table 2. We run the optimisation procedure $\tilde{B} = 50$ times and at each run of the optimisation procedure we assume that different values of the input vector are considered and different cells are measured in order to minimise biases that might occur from removing sensors associated with a particular OD pair. The path demand, i.e. the input vector, for each scenario, free-flow and congested, for each run of the optimisation procedure is obtained through a Normal distribution with mean the values given in Table 2 and variance

equal to 10% of the mean value for the free-flow scenario and 20% for the congested scenario.

	OD pair	Candidate paths	Paths carrying demand	Path demand, u (veh/h) (free-flow)	Path demand, u (veh/h) (congestion)
1	$W_{10}W_{34}$	26 → 27 → 28 → 29 → 30 → 31 → 32 → → 49 → 50 → 51 → 59 → 60 → 61 → 65	Yes	55	110
2	$W_{10}W_{56}$	26 → 34 → 35 → 36 → 37 → 38 → 56 → → 57 → 58 → 55	Yes	50	80
3	$W_{10}W_{56}$	26 → 27 → 28 → 29 → 45 → 44 → 43 → → 42 → 41 → 40 → 56 → 57 → 58 → 55	Yes	60	100
4	$W_{10}W_{56}$	26 → 27 → 28 → 29 → 30 → 31 → 32 → → 49 → 50 → 51 → 59 → 53 → 54 → 55	No	-	-
5	$W_{10}W_{56}$	26 → 27 → 28 → 29 → 45 → 44 → 43 → → 46 → 47 → 48 → 52 → 53 → 54 → 55	No	-	-
6	$W_{10}W_{48}$	26 → 34 → 35 → 36 → 37 → 38 → 39	Yes	80	120
7	$W_{10}W_{48}$	26 → 27 → 28 → 29 → 45 → 44 → 45 → → 42 → 41 → 40 → 39	No	-	-
8	W_7W_{48}	14 → 15 → 16 → 34 → 35 → 36 → 37 → → 38 → 39	Yes	75	135
9	W_7W_{48}	14 → 15 → 16 → 27 → 28 → 29 → 45 → → 44 → 43 → 42 → 41 → 40 → 39	No	-	-
10	W_7W_{48}	6 → 5 → 4 → 17 → 18 → 19 → 45 → → 44 → 43 → 42 → 41 → 40 → 39	No	-	-
11	W_7W_{56}	14 → 15 → 16 → 34 → 35 → 36 → 37 → → 38 → 56 → 57 → 58 → 55	Yes	30	75
12	W_7W_{56}	14 → 15 → 16 → 27 → 28 → 29 → 45 → → 44 → 43 → 42 → 41 → 40 → 56 → 57 → 58 → 55	Yes	50	100
13	W_7W_{56}	6 → 5 → 4 → 17 → 18 → 19 → 45 → → 44 → 43 → 42 → 41 → 40 → 56 → 57 → 58 → 55	No	-	-
14	W_7W_{56}	6 → 5 → 4 → 10 → 11 → 12 → 20 → → 21 → 22 → 49 → 50 → 51 → 52 → 53 → 54 → 55	No	-	-
15	W_7W_{56}	6 → 5 → 4 → 17 → 18 → 19 → 30 → → 31 → 32 → 49 → 50 → 51 → 52 → 53 → 54 → 55	Yes	55	90
16	W_7W_{56}	6 → 5 → 4 → 17 → 18 → 19 → 45 → → 44 → 43 → 46 → 47 → 48 → 52 → 53 → 54 → 55	No	-	-
17	W_7W_{34}	14 → 15 → 16 → 27 → 28 → 29 → 45 → → 44 → 43 → 46 → 47 → 48 → 59 → 60 → 61 → 65	No	-	-
18	W_7W_{34}	14 → 15 → 16 → 27 → 28 → 29 → 30 → → 31 → 32 → 49 → 50 → 51 → 59 → 60 → 61 → 65	Yes	45	90
19	W_7W_{34}	6 → 5 → 4 → 10 → 11 → 12 → 23 → → 24 → 25 → 62 → 63 → 64 → 65	No	-	-
20	W_7W_{34}	6 → 5 → 4 → 10 → 11 → 12 → 20 → → 21 → 22 → 49 → 50 → 51 → 59 → 60 → 61 → 65	Yes	65	100
21	W_7W_{34}	6 → 5 → 4 → 17 → 18 → 19 → 45 → → 44 → 43 → 46 → 47 → 48 → 59 → 60 → 61 → 65	No	-	-
22	W_7W_{34}	6 → 5 → 4 → 17 → 18 → 19 → 30 → → 31 → 32 → 49 → 50 → 51 → 59 → 60 → 61 → 65	Yes	75	75
23	W_7W_{35}	6 → 5 → 4 → 10 → 11 → 12 → 23 →			

		→44→43→46→47→48→52→53→54	Yes	65	105
51	W_1W_{51}	1→2→3→17→18→19→30→ →31→32→49→50→51→52→53→54	Yes	35	70
52	W_1W_{51}	1→2→3→10→→11→12→20→ →21→22→49→50→51→52→53→54	No	-	-
53	W_1W_{51}	7→8→9→20→21→22→49→ →50→51→52→53→54	No	-	-
54	W_7W_{33}	14→15→16→27→28→29→45→ →44→43→46→47→48→59→60→61	Yes	80	160
55	W_7W_{33}	14→15→16→27→28→29→30→ →31→32→49→50→51→59→60→61	No	-	-
56	W_7W_{33}	6→5→4→10→11→12→23→ →24→25→62→63→64	Yes	25	55
57	W_7W_{33}	6→5→4→10→11→12→20→ →21→22→49→50→51→59→60→61	No	-	-
58	W_7W_{33}	6→5→4→17→18→19→45→ →44→43→46→47→48→59→60→61	Yes	35	80
59	W_7W_{33}	6→5→4→17→18→19→30→ →31→32→49→50→51→59→60→61	No	-	-
60	W_7W_{51}	14→15→16→34→35→36→37→ →38→56→57→58	Yes	75	125
61	W_7W_{51}	14→15→16→27→28→29→45→ →44→43→42→41→40→56→57→58	No	-	-
62	W_7W_{51}	6→5→4→17→18→19→45→ →44→43→42→41→40→56→57→58	Yes	35	65
63	W_7W_{51}	6→5→4→10→11→12→20→ →21→22→49→50→51→52→53→54	Yes	10	20
64	W_7W_{51}	6→5→4→17→18→19→30→ →31→32→49→50→51→52→53→54	Yes	20	40
65	W_7W_{51}	6→5→4→17→18→19→45→ →44→43→46→47→48→52→53→54	No	-	-
66	W_1W_{33}	7→8→9→23→24→25→62→ →63→64	Yes	45	90
67	W_1W_{33}	7→8→9→20→21→22→49→ →50→51→59→60→61	No	-	-
68	W_1W_{33}	1→2→3→10→11→12→20→ →21→22→49→50→51→59→60→61	Yes	35	50
69	W_1W_{33}	1→2→3→17→18→19→45→ →44→43→46→47→48→59→60→61	No	-	-
70	W_1W_{33}	1→2→3→17→18→19→30→ →31→32→49→50→51→59→60→61	Yes	55	110

Table 2: Paths and path demand considered for the Nguyen-Dupuis network.